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Abstract:

This deliverable provides a description of the SSHOC Interoperability Hub functions, and references to the developed software and documentation.

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Executive Summary

The SSHOC project task 3.5 has worked with metadata and data format interoperability issues and built an interoperability hub consisting of a portal (called Conversion Hub) and selected metadata conversion solutions that the task team is currently developing. The work is based on earlier work of task 3.5 that delivered *Deliverable 3.1 Report on SSHOC (meta)data interoperability problems*, which provided an inventory of metadata and data formats used by the SSHOC communities, and recommendations for metadata standards and data file formats.

The Conversion Hub is based on a data model developed by task 3.5 team, and the Hub is built upon version 9 of CMS Drupal. Core functions for users looking for conversion solutions between research (meta)data formats include versatile search options and facet search, as well as autocompletion of search terms. The Conversion Hub also supports controlled vocabularies and includes good editorial facilities to curate and extend the information and provides an API for making the list of Conversion Solutions available in a machine-readable format.

The work on Conversion Hub will have to continue after SSHOC. The opportunities to maintain and develop the Conversion Hub after the project would be greater, and costs lower, if it were part of a wider solution or a pool of interconnected services. It should be possible to find synergy by creating, for example, common curation, technical or governance teams across various SSH services.

Generally speaking, there is an abundance of mappings between meta(data) formats, many in spreadsheet tables, but not very many ready-to-use conversion services. The shortage of available conversion services and solutions results at least partly from the lack of collaboration between communities and lack of earlier SSH cross-community projects. Projects like SSHOC are needed for pulling the different SSH communities out of their silos.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

ACDH-CH	Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage
API	application programming interface
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CIDOC CRM	International Committee for Documentation (CIDOC) Conceptual Reference Model
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CMDI	Component MetaData Infrastructure
CMS	content management system
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (The National Research Council)
CSV	comma-separated values
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DCAT-AP	Data Catalog Vocabulary Application Profile
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
EAD	Encoded Archival Description
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
FAIR	findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable
FSD	Finnish Social Science Data Archive
FORTH	Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol
IANA	Internet Assigned Numbers Authority
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ISTI	Istituto di Scienza e Tecnologie dell'Informazione "A. Faedo" (Institute of Information Science and Technologies "Alessandro Faedo")
ITEMO	IT Education Management Organisation
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LIBER	Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche
MIME	Multipurpose Internet Mail Extensions
NA	not available
OEAW	Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften (Austrian Academy of Sciences)
PEM	PARTHENOS Entities Model
PHP	PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor

RDF	Resource Description Framework
RESTORE	smaRt accESs TO digital heRitage and mEmory
SAS	Statistical Analysis System
SND	Swedish National Data Service
SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
SSH	social sciences and humanities
SSHOCro	SSHOC Reference Ontology
TEI	Text Encoding Initiative
UI	user interface
UKDS	UK Data Service
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VMT	Vocabulary Matching Tool
XML	Extensible Markup Language
XSL	Extensible Stylesheet Language
XSLT	Extensible Stylesheet Language Transformations

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

The SSHOC project aims to build the SSH (Social Science and Humanities) part of the EOSC (European Open Science Cloud). The goals of SSHOC Work Package 3 include the development, enhancement and integration of tools and services for managing and processing SSH research data, based on existing tools, functionalities, and requirements for interoperability, as well as supporting better discoverability of existing resources.

In line with these goals, task 3.5 has worked with metadata and data format interoperability issues and has built an interoperability hub. The hub consists of a web portal and selected conversion solutions. The portal contains information about available conversion services or guidance for conversion workflows and thus it is a registry of conversion solutions. It has both a human-readable user interface and an API for machines. To clarify the focus on the format conversion elements of interoperability the portal has been named 'Conversion Hub'. In addition to the portal, the task 3.5 team is in the process of producing a number of metadata conversion solutions. This report describes the SSHOC Conversion Hub and its functions, and the forthcoming metadata conversion solutions.

1.2 Background and earlier work

Earlier work of task 3.5 delivered *D3.1 Report on SSHOC (meta)data interoperability problems*, which provided an inventory of metadata and data formats used by the SSHOC communities and recommendations for metadata standards and data file formats (Broeder et al. 2019). Information on existing practices and needs was collected by interviewing experts from SSH communities. The communities differ e.g., in data types, metadata standards and data formats and each has its own established traditions that may cause interoperability issues with other communities. This existing diversity needs to be accepted since in most cases, the different formats and practices make good sense and any convergence between communities in this matter is beyond the means and time-scale of the SSHOC project. The solution is to provide and point to conversion solutions for what can be considered the major recommended metadata standards and data formats used in the SSH.

D3.1 explained the scope and defined criteria which informed the conversion solutions to be developed by task 3.5. It was followed up by an *Inventory of existing (meta-)data format interoperability solutions* that included existing metadata and data format conversions, technologies, and practices relevant to the social sciences and humanities (Kleemola et al. 2020). It laid ground for the work reported here by providing content and defining the architecture for the Conversion Hub.

The task team has identified two types of conversion solutions:

1. Ready to use (web-)services or solutions that are typically provided by research infrastructures, research centres or organisations, or commercial companies.
2. Complex solutions where the workflow can entail the use of several services and manual steps. In this report, this type of solutions is referred to as conversion recipes. A description of, and references to these workflows through the conversion hub provides the most practical and immediate benefit to users.

Regardless of the type of the solution, good documentation is important. It enables the user to find the solution, use it, refer to it, and make informed decisions about the conversions and the usability of converted data.

1.3 Relation to other SSHOC tasks and outputs

The Conversion Hub is related to SSHOC Work Package 7 that is developing the SSH Open Marketplace (see Chapter 2.4). Conversion services could be made available as choices in the SSHOC Switchboard¹ (built by the task 3.6 team). The layout of the Conversion Hub is subject to changes according to branding guidance (WP2). The technical approach is shared with the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit (WP6).

1.4 Structure of the document

Chapter 1 has described the scope and background of the work. Chapter 2 covers Conversion Hub's technology, data model and functions. Chapter 3 outlines the developed or forthcoming conversion solutions and Chapter 4 discusses sustainability after the project. Finally, Chapter 5 contains conclusions and recommendations for future work.

2. Conversion Hub

2.1 Technology and functions

The conversion solutions provided by the hub are items that curators create, edit, and publish and that visitors browse and view. This requires the management of these items, user management, and flexible means to present the content to the users. Additionally, the conversion solutions should be enriched with metadata to allow search filters and individual faceting of the content to support different use cases and perspectives when looking for a specific tool for conversion.

¹ Note that the Switchboard only invokes the conversion service which, to be useful in this context, should then be able to save the result data in a workspace or visualise it in a GUI. In task 3.6 this is ongoing work.

Based on the specifications of the Conversion Hub, a content management system (CMS) was a preferred technical solution as it comes out of the box with a user management (including user roles to allow different permission levels), an ad-hoc availability of backend and frontend, many options to implement a data model, and easy maintenance as well as little coding requirements. Due to the need for content with structured data, a CMS allowing custom data fields with different data types was needed. Another important requirement was the use of (controlled) vocabularies. These requirements limited the available and suitable CMS solutions, and based on a further evaluation and the experience by SSHOC WP3 team members, it was decided to rely on the latest stable version of CMS Drupal² (when starting development this was Drupal 8, the Conversion Hub has since been updated to Drupal 9). Not only does it fulfil the described requirements - an alternative would be the CMS WordPress but that does not support structured data and vocabularies very well - it also has a strong community, is in active development (and open source) and is well documented. Basic editing and viewing capabilities come out of the box, with no need for development work. The customisation of the data model and the look and feel is easily possible through the rich configuration options of the system via management UI. Additionally, there are many modules in Drupal to extend the functionality especially in terms of content presentation. The activation of an API integrated into Drupal allows not only decoupled approaches for the frontend but also the further processing of content by external tools. Thus, contributing to the implementation of the Conversion Hub based on the FAIR data principles.

The Conversion Hub has been implemented and available at <https://conversion-hub.sshopencloud.eu>³ and is hosted by WP3 partner DARIAH/OEAW ACDH-CH (Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage). It is based on the defined system specification and the data model (see chapter 2.3). The ACDH-CH runs several Drupal-based applications and therefore has the expertise, workflows, and the technical infrastructure to cover all necessary implementation steps as well as the maintenance and secure storing of the code and the data. Good software development practice is ensured⁴, e.g., version control of the code and the configuration of the Conversion Hub. This ensures easy adaptation of the system and long-term availability. The availability of a documented API makes it possible to separate the data (the content) from the CMS and to re-use it in many ways. Therefore, it is possible to integrate the conversion solution items with simple means e.g., in the SSH Open Marketplace. A similar technical approach by ACDH-CH is also used for the development of the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit in SSHOC WP6, lowering the overall maintenance cost.

The general aim of the Conversion Hub is to collect information about conversion tools and solutions and to allow for different ways of searching and exploring them. Useful features to achieve this goal were implemented mainly based on either functions available in Drupal core or by integrating modules from

² CMS Drupal: <https://drupal.org> (accessed Sept 2021)

³ Conversion Hub available via SSHOC website subdomain: <https://conversion-hub.sshopencloud.eu> (accessed Sept 2021)

⁴ Following the software development recommendations within SSHOC.

the Drupal ecosystem. The main functionalities that guided the implementation of the Conversion Hub include user management, content management, comments, API, structured data, faceted search, search options and input form. These are described below.

User management. By relying on the core user management of Drupal, additional versioning of content is activated. The Conversion Hub is freely available on the internet, so visitors do not need to have a user account. Curators can be created by administrators. It was decided to use the basic Drupal user management that gives a good way to overview the active registered users (curators) on the platform. The user roles are described in Table 1.

Table 1. Conversion Hub user roles

Visitor	User that cannot edit, often also called end-user.
Curator	Registered user with editing rights. There are two types of curators: moderators and contributors. Contributors' editing rights are restricted to their own content.
Administrator	User that can create and manage all aspects of Hub.
User	Any user (visitor, curator [moderator, contributor], administrator)

Content management. Permitted interaction with content depends on user roles. Administrators and moderators can apply all methods of modification, e.g., rejecting changes of data by restoring a former version of an item. Contributors are limited to the manipulation of their own content. Visitors are only able to see released content without a way to modify the data.

Comments. It is possible to add comments to items contextualising the information or proposing editorial changes. Comments are visible to all users, including visitors, but commenting is restricted to curators. Even though it would be possible to open the commenting functionality for visitors, it was decided not to do so as this would require a continuous moderation of the incoming comments.

API. Drupal comes with a built-in API, which enables third party consumers like the SSH Open Marketplace to programmatically access information in the Conversion Hub⁵. The default API is based on the JSON API specification⁶, delivering a well-established, structured, and documented interface for retrieving metadata from the Conversion Hub, with a OpenAPI/Swagger specification⁷, describing individual endpoints and the returned data⁸. This allows for easy re-use of the information about the

⁵ The JSON:API module is part of Drupal core and comes out of the box. After activation it publishes the content based on the JSON:API specification, see the Drupal documentation: <https://www.drupal.org/docs/core-modules-and-themes/core-modules/jsonapi-module/jsonapi> (accessed Sept 2021)

⁶ JSON:API specification: <https://jsonapi.org/> (accessed Sept 2021)

⁷ OpenAPI/Swagger specification: <https://www.openapis.org/> (accessed Sept 2021)

⁸ The API endpoint is available at <https://conversion-hub.sshopencloud.eu/jsonapi>

conversion tools by other platforms, like the SSH Open Marketplace, where with the help of the API this collection will be referenced. It is also possible to use the API to search for specific conversion tools and to implement alternative frontend solutions or services based on the data in the Conversion Hub. For the API, a project specific documentation - next to the official documentation on the Drupal website - will be available when the Conversion Hub is released.

```

▶ jsonapi: {..}
▼ data:
  ▼ 0:
    type: "node--solution"
    id: "847a8971-c4b9-46e4-94a1-31ae144fb775"
    ▶ links: {..}
    ▼ attributes:
      drupal_internal__nid: 51
      drupal_internal__vid: 55
      langcode: "en"
      revision_timestamp: "2021-02-23T18:36:23+00:00"
      revision_log: null
      status: true
      title: "Audacity"
      created: "2021-02-23T18:36:23+00:00"
      changed: "2021-02-23T18:36:23+00:00"
      promote: false
      sticky: false
      default_langcode: true
      revision_translation_affected: true
      ▶ path: {..}
      body: null
      comment: null
      field_alternative_name: []
      ▶ field_contact: {..}
      ▼ field_input_format_comment:
        value: "multiple formats"
        format: "basic_html"
        processed: "multiple formats"
      field_isrecipe: null
      field_last_modification_date: null
      field_last_modification_text: "2020"
      ▼ field_license_text:
        ▼ 0: "GPL2 https://www.gnu.org/licenses/old-licenses/gpl-2.0.en.html"
      ▶ field_output_format_comment: {..}
      field_publication_date: null
      field_publication_text: "?"
      field_see_also: []
      field_source: []
      ▼ field_url:
        ▼ 0:
          uri: "https://www.audacityteam.org/"
          title: null
          options: []
      ▶ relationships: {..}
  ▼ 1:
    type: "node--solution"
  
```

Figure 1. Output of an API call getting all conversion solutions. In the screenshot parts of the API information on the conversion solution “Audacity” are visible.

Structured data. For the formulation of the data model for the Conversion Hub it was decided to apply a strongly structured data approach (see chapter 2.2 for the data model). Alongside the development of the Conversion Hub the data model evolved, thus introducing new metadata fields and new vocabularies. Drupal offers a flexible content type management (see Figure 2), where new fields can be added on the fly and can be associated with a vocabulary restricting the allowed values, or other data types like dates, boolean or text. This allows for a rapid prototyping approach, i.e., the implementation of new features based on the feedback from the users.

Home » Administration » Structure » Content types » Solution

[+ Add field](#)

LABEL	MACHINE NAME	FIELD TYPE	OPERATIONS
Alternative name	field_alternative_name	Text (plain)	Edit
Application category	field_application_category	Entity reference	Edit
Application sub-category	field_application_sub_category	Entity reference	Edit
Comments	comment	Comments	Edit
Community	field_community	Entity reference	Edit

Figure 2. Content management view showing some of the Conversion Hub field definitions of the main content type “Solution”

Faceted search. Some fields are designed to be used in a faceted search. This means that search results can be filtered by the values of these fields. Usually this makes sense for fields based on vocabularies like *invocation type* or *community*. The facets on *input* and *output formats* are particularly helpful for using the Conversion Hub. Visitors can start by filtering the overview list by an *input format* and immediately get all tools that support this specific format as input. They can then drill down the result by filtering along other facets like the *output format*. By doing so visitors can see the tools that support the combination of input and output format, e.g., all tools that allow conversion from input format “XML” to output format “ntriples”.

Search options. Different ways are implemented for visitors of the Conversion Hub to search for relevant conversion solutions. The default option is to enter a search term in a search bar. The search bar features autocomplete, allowing visitors to either directly go to the detail page of one of the solutions listed in the autocomplete popup or retrieve the search result set based on the entered search term. Searches

are conducted against multiple metadata fields associated with the conversion solution item, including title and input and output format. Thus, it is possible to directly search for tools that use a format either as input or output format, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Search bar with suggestions for solution names

If more than one search key is typed to the search field, the operator used between them is “AND” meaning that all the search keys must appear in the result. If there is a search key that is not wanted in the result, then the minus sign must be used before the search key. Another way to explore the information in the Conversion Hub is to browse through the overview list (displayed by default to visitors when they arrive) or by reducing the available tools based on selected criteria in the facets in the left side panel, e.g. “Community”. The system also runs a simple search, when visitors click the links embedded in the description of the solutions information page (Figure 4), e.g., “DDI Codebook 2.5” under the title “Input format”. All these approaches are well known and intuitive ways of searching data. By combining them and building on structured data, the Conversion Hub helps users in finding relevant conversion tools for their needs. It is expected that the most common searches will be for input and output formats. Therefore, these criteria have dedicated facets and are included in the autocomplete mechanism for simple search.

Kuha2

Solution

<p>Is a recipe No</p> <p>Description Kuha2 is a metadata server that provides descriptive social science research metadata for harvesting via multiple protocols and a growing variety of metadata standards. The software is a collection of applications and consists of three server applications, a client application and a database.</p> <p>Input format DDI Codebook 1.2.2 DDI Codebook 2.5 DDI Lifecycle 3.1</p>	<p>Link to landing page The Documentation of Kuha2 Kuha2 repository</p> <p>Status maintained</p> <p>Source The Documentation of Kuha2 FSD's Open Source Softwares</p> <p>Contact Toni Sissala / Finnish Social Scienc</p>
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Figure 4. The information page of the solution called Kuha2 with embedded links

Input form. Curators of the Conversion Hub will be responsible for collecting and curating the necessary metadata about conversion solutions. The Conversion Hub data input form that is based on the data model supports the curator in categorising and contextualising the solution. As most of the metadata fields are fed by vocabularies, the input form allows curators to choose a suitable option from a list of values (which are usually controlled). Being a standard Drupal input form, it provides a way to enter the information in a structured and controlled manner. Figure 5 shows *multi-select fields* (“Community” and “Invocation type”), *single-value select field* (“Expected Level of Knowledge”) and a *date field* (“Publication date”).

The input and output formats are based on the IANA media types vocabulary⁹, therefore making many different format options available. Upon entering characters into the autocomplete select field, a list of possible values will appear; the curators will then choose the correct one, thus avoiding different spellings as shown in Figure 6.

It is possible to save an entry as a draft. This allows the curator to withhold the data of a new solution item until it meets the quality criteria for publishing.

⁹ IANA media types vocabulary: <https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/media-types.xhtml>. See also ch. 2.3.

Community

CESSDA

CLARIN

cross-community

DARIAH

ERIHS

LIBER

This attribute describes which SSHOC community uses the solution (primarily).

Invocation type

command line

command processor

instruction page

library

local application

RESTful webservice

script

source code

source code/RESTful webservice

source code/web application

web application

Expected Level of Knowledge

advanced ▼

Publication date

TT . MM . JJJJ

Figure 5. Information can be entered in a structured and controlled manner

FORMATS [Show row weights](#)

INPUT FORMAT

✚

- MARC21 (XML)
- RDF/XML
- XML

Add

Input format comment

B I | | | | Format ▼ | Source

Figure 6. The input format text field has an autocomplete feature

Summing up the technology decisions of the Conversion Hub:

1. The Conversion Hub platform is built upon the widely adapted open-source content management system Drupal (using the coding language PHP and a MariaDB database).
2. The most recent version of Drupal is used, together with a few community contributed modules to extend the functionality, e.g. implementing an autocomplete mechanism.
3. The choice of the technology was based on the need for the implementation of a flexible content model and content creation strategy involving a number of curators recruited from the partners in WP3. This decision was further reinforced by the comprehensive user and permissions management and content versioning methods of the Drupal CMS.
4. Another important argument for the technology decision was the ability to implement a complex data model for describing the conversion solutions that allowed the use of (controlled) vocabularies, which was of particular importance.
5. There was also a demand to use a technology that features an API out of the box, adhering to community-based specifications.
6. These technology aspects enable a good search and discovery experience for visitors, easy editing and creating of items by curators, and re-use of the data by external services - like the SSH Open Marketplace - following the FAIR data principles.

2.2 Data model

Every solution included in the Conversion Hub is described with a number of attributes (also called metadata fields or metadata elements). The attributes form the core of the Conversion Hub data model, and many of the attributes rely on controlled vocabularies instead of free textual descriptions. The aim in delivering structured descriptions of the solutions is not only to support a targeted search for conversion solutions, but also to allow for and stimulate machine-driven re-use of the metadata. For example, one can think of showing a list of conversion solutions based on their output format, making use of the structured metadata exposed via the API.

Whenever possible, the attributes were taken from, or mapped to, schema.org and SSHOCro. In the SSHOCro mapping, a number of classes/properties from CIDOC CRM (Es and Ps) and PEM (PEs and PPs) have been used instead of relying mostly on SSHOCro (SHEs and SHRs). This was done intentionally, as the SSHOCro is being updated (resulting in substantial revisions). The goal is to produce new mappings which will reflect the final state of SSHOCro by the end of January 2022.

The first version of the attributes was presented in the MS14 report and formed the basis of the data model. The list of attributes is presented in Table 2 below and the full Conversion Hub data model is included as Appendix A.

Table 2. Conversion Hub data model attributes

Attribute	Short description
Solution name	Name of the conversion solution.
Alternative name	Alternate name of the solution.
Link to landing page	URL of the solution and link text.
Description	Short textual description of the solution.
Community	Which SSHOC community uses the solution (primarily).
Invocation type	Description of how the service can be used/called.
Condition of use: Local use	Used to indicate under which terms the solution can be installed or operated locally.
Condition of use: Operate service	Used to indicate under which terms the solution can be installed or operated as a service and offered to third parties.
Condition of use: Further development	Used to indicate under which terms the solution can be integrated or changed.
Terms of Use / License	The license document that applies to this content, typically indicated by URL.
Input format	Description of the media type (MIME type) of the input file(s).
Input format comment	Further information on the input format.
Output format	Description of the media type (MIME type) of the output file(s).
Output format comment	Further information on the output format.
Status	Status of the solution in terms of its lifecycle stage.
Publication date	Time when the solution first appeared with the exact date or free text.
Last modification date	Time when the solution was most recently modified with the exact date or free text.
Expected level of knowledge	Level of knowledge the user of the solution is expected to have.
Application category	Type of the solution, used by the Marketplace.
Application sub-category	Subtype of the solution, used by the Marketplace.
See Also	Resources that are related to the solution.
Source	Source(s) that were used to create the Conversion Hub entry.
Related Tool	Tool that is closely related to the conversion solution or the reason the conversion exists.
Is Recipe	Indicates if the conversion solution is a recipe.
Contact	Main contact point of the described conversion solution.

2.3 Contents

The selection of solutions to be included in the Conversion Hub has been described in the MS14 report and in D3.1. Priority was given to solutions relevant for several SSHOC communities or for cross-community use, and to solutions pertaining to the SSHOC recommended formats as defined in D3.1. At the time of writing, the Conversion Hub contains 46 solutions. One third of the solutions have been categorised as cross-community¹⁰ solutions (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Number of solutions in Conversion Hub by community (note that the same solution can be listed under more than one community)

Most solutions require an advanced or expert level of knowledge before they can be used, such as a deep knowledge of the structure of the source and the target metadata schemas and knowledge in underlying concepts and technology (Figure 8). Only about a fourth have been categorized as suitable for novice users. This is a clear barrier for using many of the conversion solutions. In some cases, adding documentation would be sufficient to enable use without extensive prior knowledge about the (meta)data formats, and some solutions are candidates for developing into easy-to-use web services. For the latter approach it is important that the licenses and ownership of solutions are clearly stated.

¹⁰ Cross-community solutions refer to solutions that are, by design, intended to be used by several (SSH) communities.

Figure 8. Expected level of knowledge needed to use the solutions (n=46)

The most common input and output formats for meta(data) conversion solutions in the Conversion Hub are DDI (various versions), TEI, csv, ntriples, SAS and SPSS sav. In total, 39 different input formats and 44 output formats are listed when different versions of the same metadata schema are counted separately. Further work is needed to find the optimal way to describe the input and output formats in cases where the media type is not sufficient or when a clearer distinction between form and content is needed. For example, an XML file could be for example DDI or TEI, and a DDI file could in turn be instantiated as XML or RDF or more.

The Conversion Hub content is subject to changes, improvements and additions, and the solutions that are being developed by task 3.5 (see Chapter 3) will be added by the end of the project.

2.4 Link to SSH Open Marketplace

The SSH Open Marketplace¹¹ is the main product of SSHOC WP7, a structured catalogue where researchers of the SSH community can look for tools, services, training materials and workflows as well as references of these items to publications and datasets. It ingests information from various sources, especially from outcomes developed by other work packages in SSHOC. WP3's Conversion Hub is one of these sources as it contains references to tools and services including rich metadata. To allow a good

¹¹ SSH Open Marketplace: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/> (accessed Sept 2021)

search experience the SSH Open Marketplace relies on such metadata, making the Conversion Hub an ideal candidate for ingesting data into the SSH Open Marketplace.

Thanks to some members of SSHOC WP3 also participating in the development of WP7's SSH Open Marketplace, convergence of Conversion Hub and SSH Open Marketplace was taken into consideration from the very beginning. Many of the Conversion Hub metadata fields have the same or equivalent fields in the SSH Open Marketplace. This situation made it easy to come up with a mapping between the data model of the Conversion Hub and the SSH Open Marketplace, which is required for implementing the source-specific ingestion pipelines. Relevant metadata from the Conversion Hub can be imported and expressed in the SSH Open Marketplace. The conversion solutions can be split into two basic categories of the SSH Open Marketplace: conversion tools are mapped to the *tools and services* category whereas conversion recipes can be mapped to the *workflows* category. Accommodating recipes in the Conversion Hub is an area where more work is needed. Not all recipes are 'simple' workflows ready for automation; some recipes, or part of recipes, need human interpretation.

An important part of the mapping is agreeing on similar or related vocabularies. As there was awareness about this already in the drafting phase of the Conversion Hub data model, the chosen vocabularies are in line with the ones used by the SSH Open Marketplace. There are even vocabularies that are re-used by the SSH Open Marketplace like the vocabulary on invocation types. By re-using the same community-agreed vocabularies - when available - in both platforms, an ideal mapping foundation was established. An example of a vocabulary that is used in both services is the IANA Media Types. It is referred to by the input and output format of the Conversion Hub and used by the SSH Open Marketplace for the object-format property.

The SSH Open Marketplace has a generic data model and can be seen more as a catalogue of metadata on SSH resources. Conversion Hub provides the users detailed information about the solutions as well as the possibility to limit the search using facets specific to conversion solutions. In addition, the SSH Open Marketplace is focused on harvesting data and connecting information from different sources and not on creating new content like the Conversion Hub where a dedicated CMS is in place. Therefore, it is reasonable to keep the Conversion Hub active even though metadata is ingested into the SSH Open Marketplace. There will be a mechanism for continuous ingestions of new items from the Conversion Hub to the SSH Open Marketplace. The ingestion pipeline of the SSH Open Marketplace uses the API of the Conversion Hub. The SSH Open Marketplace records about conversion solutions need to have, on the one hand, direct links to the solutions, and on the other hand, links to the Conversion Hub.

The SSH Open Marketplace collects data from many sources and enriches them, especially by establishing links between related items, e.g., relating a tool to a training material in which it is described or used. It is expected that some of the conversion solutions are also featured in other sources of the SSH Open Marketplace, so that information from multiple sources will come together in the Marketplace, including connections between the different SSH resources. This allows curators of the Conversion Hub to potentially discover new conversion solutions and to enrich the metadata of the Conversion Hub

items. The mention of the Conversion Hub as a source in the SSH Open Marketplace will additionally attract new visitors to this outcome of WP3.

An example of a service that could be linked via the SSH Marketplace is the CLARIN Language Resource Switchboard. Originally it was thought that a suitable integration between the Conversion Hub and the Switchboard can be achieved at the level of user interface, or at least at the level of exchange information about the suitable conversion services, by exchanging conversion service metadata. However, as the SSHOC project developed, it turned out to be better to use the SSH Open Marketplace (WP7) as the rallying point of any information exchange. Both the Conversion Hub and the Switchboard are harvested by the SSH Open Marketplace and will become subject to the Marketplace’s editorial process. This should lead to having the conversion services available as choices in the Switchboard.

3. Conversion solutions under development

The selection of conversion solutions to be developed by task 3.5 was based on D3.1 and MS14, as well as the available resources. The solutions are described in Table 3 below. All of them are currently in development and the work will continue until the end of the SSHOC project. All developed solutions will be made openly available, and the descriptions included in the Conversion Hub.

Table 3. Conversion solutions being developed by task 3.5

Solution	Description	Developed by
DDI - CMDI	XSLT stylesheet to convert from Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) to Component MetaData Infrastructure (CMDI) to enable harvesting and processing metadata for discovery.	CLARIN ERIC
DDI - META-SHARE	New XSLT stylesheet for conversion between DDI and META-SHARE metadata model that describes language resources.	SND
DDI - DCAT-AP	New XSLT stylesheet for conversion between DDI and the DCAT Application Profile for data portals in Europe.	SND
DDI - ISO 19115	New XSLT stylesheet for conversion between DDI and ISO	SND
DDI transformations upgrade	Update of existing XSLT for DDI transformations to facilitate newer versions of DDI.	SND
Profile for natural science	XSLT for conversion of relevant metadata standards to and from DDI	SND
Profile for Technology	XSLT for conversion of relevant metadata standards to and from DDI	SND
TEI - CMDI	Mapping from TEI to CMDI and a mapping service	OEAW

Raw data to RDF	<p>Document that highlights the E-RIHS / RESTORE / DARIAH-IT data management pipeline that leads to the transformation of the data initially collected from the various sources (XML EAD and EAC files, Descriptive records of artworks, texts encoded in the TEI...), to their final triplication (RDF format) in accordance with the CIDOC-CRM ontology.</p> <p>The workflow resolves technical uncertainties and problems of different sides, starting from the acquisition of the data to its reuse and is used in the "RESTORE" Data Pilot described in SSHOC MS49.</p>	DARIAH.it/CNR
X3ML Toolkit recipe	<p>Recipe supported by examples and screenshots for using the suite developed by FORTH, which transforms XML data into RDF. The resources converted to RDF will be modelled according to one of the initially selectable schemes (the recipe uses CIDOC-CRM as example). This recipe was produced while working on the "RESTORE" Data Pilot developed in SSHOC.</p>	DARIAH.it/CNR
Karma recipe	<p>This recipe contains information about installing and using Karma. Karma is a free open source data integration tool and can be used to map data in a variety of formats and from a variety of data sources (databases, spreadsheets, XML...) to structured RDF. It also allows the creation of links to external resources (such as DBpedia or GeoNames).</p> <p>This recipe was produced while working on the "RESTORE" Data Pilot developed in SSHOC.</p>	DARIAH.it/CNR
Vocabulary Matching Tool	<p>An experimental tool, based on the Ariadne VMT, to aid users in the creation of mappings from locally used terms/concepts to one of the controlled vocabularies (to be defined which one) individuated in D3.1. The tool can be used to map different vocabularies in a common spine vocabulary, helping the implementation of semantic interoperability.</p>	CNR

4. Sustainability

During the SSHOC project, the Conversion Hub content has been maintained by task 3.5 team members from four SSH communities: CESSDA, CLARIN, DARIAH and E-RIHS. The technology has been hosted by DARIAH/OEAW ACDH-CH (see ch. 2.1). This division of work has worked well. This chapter presents options for sustaining the Conversion Hub after the SSHOC project based on the experiences during the project.

The recommended roles and their tasks for Conversion Hub administration and maintenance are listed in Table 4. The roles are based on the draft of the SSH Open Marketplace governance model¹². Each role can be taken by a person or a team and one person or one team can perform multiple roles. It is envisioned that the roles are spread across SSH organisations that cooperate to provide the Conversion Hub. The details of implementing the maintenance of Conversion Hub need to be agreed by the organisations taking the roles. Standards like FitSM¹³ can be helpful in determining details.

Table 4. Conversion Hub maintenance roles

Role	Main task(s)	Notes
Governing Board	Defines the scientific orientation of the Conversion Hub. Defines the work plan which should be regularly updated.	The scientific orientation as defined in the SSH Open Marketplace governance model is the orientation chosen to foster the offer and effectiveness with regards to SSH research's needs and challenges. For Conversion Hub, a separate Governing Board is not necessary, the decisions can be made on the level of the Editorial Board.
Owner	Overall responsibility for all Conversion Hub activities. The primary contact point for Conversion Hub.	Ideally one person.
Technology host	Technical implementation and hosting of Conversion Hub. Maintenance of Conversion Hub documentation and specifications.	

¹² SSHOC D7.5 Marketplace – Governance v0.4 (internal unpublished document)

¹³ FitSM is a free and lightweight standards family aimed at enabling effective IT service management. It was developed through the FedSM Project, funded by the European Commission, and is now maintained by ITEM. <https://www.fitsm.eu/> (accessed Sept 2021)

Editorial Board	Management of Conversion Hub content. Selection of solutions to be included in Conversion Hub.	Ideal size for the Editorial Board is around five members. The members should represent the different SSH communities, and it is recommended that the Editorial Board is composed of Curators.
Curator	Content curation and editing. Maintenance of designated descriptions of solutions in Conversion Hub to ensure that they are up-to-date and valid.	Curators should be experts from the different SSH communities.

Three potential scenarios for hosting, maintenance and development of the Conversion Hub are envisioned:

- A. Basic hosting and maintenance through to replacement or obsolescence of the product, editorial actions only per request and if action is needed due to legislation.
- B. A + ongoing editorial control and addition of solutions over time.
- C. B + active research and development of content and technology, based on users' needs and technological advances.

The costs will increase from A to C but overall, the costs of keeping Conversion Hub up and running after the SSHOC project are moderate. Three kinds of costs apply: operational costs (hardware, technical maintenance), curation costs (intellectual maintenance) and governing costs (governance, outreach)¹⁴. In a minimum scenario A, the Technology Host would fix bugs and implement any security updates, but content would not be edited unless there are legal reasons to do so. Scenario B adds checking the validity of existing descriptions, addition of descriptions of possibly 5-10 new items annually and removal of non-working items. The most ambitious scenario C would also include new functionalities, creation of new conversion recipes, more new descriptions, and outreach and more communication with the visitors and research community. There would be no governance in scenario A and governance would be very limited in scenarios B and C. It is worth noting that in the course of only a few years, scenarios A and B will lead to obsolescence of hardware and software technology. The estimated costs for scenario B are presented in Table 5.

¹⁴ These three categories follow the SSH Open Marketplace cost scenarios in SSHOC D7.5 Marketplace – Governance v0.4 (unpublished at time of writing).

Table 5. Estimation of Conversion Hub costs annually (scenario B: basic hosting and maintenance through to replacement or obsolescence and ongoing editorial control and addition of solutions)

Cost item	Annual cost
Operational costs	€ 2000
Content costs	1 PM annually, appr. € 6000
Governing costs	0.2 PM annually, appr. € 1200

Any investment above scenario B would help to improve the Conversion Hub’s quality and uptake. The value of the service is in the data model and the content - and the value of content grows over time - so resources should be geared towards curation and development of new functionalities that benefit the SSH researchers.

It is envisioned that in-kind contributions by SSH ERICs would be available and that development could be taken up by new projects. The opportunities to maintain and develop the Conversion Hub would be greater, and costs lower, if it were part of a wider solution or a pool of interconnected services. The roles defined in Table 4 are general enough to be applicable to a range of other SSH services and it should be possible to find synergy by creating, for example, common curation, technical or governance teams across SSH services. The level to which costs could be defrayed by sharing roles across contractual services depends on the specific model and partnerships involved. The forthcoming outputs of SSHOC WP8 will need to be considered when agreeing on the maintenance of Conversion Hub after the project.

For the individual conversion solutions (Table 3) the expectation is that the organisations that developed them will sustain them after the project, but their maintenance will have to be agreed on before the end of the project.

5. Conclusion

Task 3.5 has worked with metadata and data format interoperability issues and has built a Conversion Hub that contains information about available conversion services or guidance for conversion workflows (recipes). In addition, the team is developing selected conversion solutions for the SSH community.

The Conversion Hub is based on a data model developed by task 3.5 team, and the Hub is built upon version 9 of CMS Drupal. The general aim of the Conversion Hub is to collect information about conversion tools and solutions and to allow for different ways of searching and exploring them. Core functions include versatile search options and facet search, as well as autocompletion of search terms. The Conversion Hub also supports controlled vocabularies and includes good editorial facilities to curate and extend the information. The potential convergence of Conversion Hub and SSH Open Marketplace was taken into consideration as an efficient solution for sustainability but proved impractical from perspectives of specificity and required curation options. The Conversion Hub will be one of the tools listed in the SSH Open Marketplace. In addition, the Conversion Hub will be a source for the SSH Open Marketplace, and the ingestion pipeline will use the API of the Conversion Hub.

Future work on Conversion Hub will include creating policy documents and content management guidance and enhancing the technical and user documentation. Further editing and adding of content is also needed, and the used vocabularies assessed and modified where necessary. Recipes need to be accommodated better, and the data model should be refined based on users' needs. The descriptions of the solutions could include more information on, for example, the media type, the lossiness of conversion, the quality of conversion output, and if the conversion process can be fully automated. The work will have to continue after the project. For the API, a project specific documentation - next to the official documentation on the Drupal website - will be available when the Conversion Hub is released.

The opportunities to maintain and develop the Conversion Hub after the project would be greater, and costs lower, if it were part of a wider solution or a pool of interconnected services. It should be possible to find synergy by creating, for example, common curation, technical or governance teams across various SSH services.

Generally speaking, there is an abundance of mappings between meta(data) formats, many in spreadsheet tables, but not very many ready-to-use conversion services. The shortage of available conversion services and solutions results at least partly from the lack of collaboration between communities and lack of earlier SSH cross-community projects. Projects like SSHOC are needed for pulling the different SSH communities out of their silos.

6. References

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Appendix A. SSHOC Conversion Hub data model

Version 1.1 (2021-09-15)

This data model includes the attributes (or metadata elements) that are used to describe the conversion solutions in the Conversion Hub. Mappings to schema.org and SSHOCro 1.1.3¹⁵ are included when available. An example can be found in the last row of each table.

Attribute	Solution name
Repeatability	Mandatory, non-Repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	
Description	Name of the conversion solution.
Mappings	https://schema.org/name SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool.P1 is identified by: E41 Appellation, AND SHE10 Tool. P2 has type: E55 Type {= "Digital"}, AND SHE10 Tool. P2 has type: E55 Type {= "Conversion solution"} ¹⁶
Example	Kuha2

Attribute	Alternative name
Repeatability	Optional, Repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	
Description	Alternate name of the solution.

¹⁵ SSHOCro v. 1.3.3 is available as part of: Eleni Tsouloucha, Athina Kritsotaki, Chryssoula Bekiari, & Maria Theodoridou. (2021). D4.19 linked files. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5106461>

¹⁶ The types assigned to SSHOCro classes in {curly brackets} correspond to types that the transformation algorithm must take into account. In this particular case, the conversion solution is considered to lie in the extension of Digital Object and Tool. To distinguish it from other suchlike digital tools, we also mark that it is of type "Conversion Solution" as well. Furthermore, the constant types assigned to SHE10 Tool - i.e. "Digital" and "Conversion solution" - are inherited throughout the mappings, and need not be repeated.

Mappings	https://schema.org/alternateName SSHOCro: SSHE10 Tool.P1 is identified by: E41 Appellation. P2 has type: E55 Type {"Alternative Name"},
Example	

Attribute	Link to landing page
Repeatability	Optional, repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	
Description	URL of the solution and link text.
Mapping	https://schema.org/url SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool. PP50 accessible at: PE29 Access Point
Example	Kuha2 repository https://bitbucket.org/tietoarkisto/workspace/projects/KUH

Attribute	Description
Repeatability	Optional, non-repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	
Description	A short textual description of the solution.
Mapping	https://schema.org/description SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool. P3 has note: E62 String
Example	Kuha2 is a metadata server that provides descriptive social science research metadata for harvesting via multiple protocols and a growing variety of metadata standards. The software is a collection of applications and consists of three server applications, a client application and a database.

Attribute	Community
Repeatability	Optional, repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	custom vocabulary: {CLARIN, DARIAH, cross-community, CESSDA, LIBER, ERIHS}
Description	This attribute describes which SSHOC community uses the solution (primarily). Cross-community = not intended to be domain specific.
Mapping	https://schema.org/audience SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool. P19i was made for: E7 Activity.P14 carried out by: E39 Actor. P2 has type: E55 Type {"Community"}
Example	CESSDA

Attribute	Invocation type
Repeatability	Optional, repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	Custom vocabulary: command line; command processor; instruction page; library; local application; RESTful webservice; script; source code; source code/RESTful webservice; source code/web application; web application <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Command line: to be invoked via command line, implies that either the source code or a binary distribution is available (includes Java applications without UI) ● Command processor - an application that has the ability to interpret commands or execute whole scripts. ● Instruction page: a human interpretable description to perform a task or how to invoke specific services to perform a task ● Library: compiled source code that provides a programming API ● Local application: a compiled software with user interface that needs to be installed on the user's personal device ● RESTful webservice: solution with programmatic interface accessible via HTTP (according to RESTful principles) ● Script: includes scripts, e.g. XSL scripts ● Source code: programming language statements ● Source code/RESTful webservice: source code to be run as a programmatic interface accessible via HTTP ● Source code/web application: source code to be run as a web application

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Web application: solution with user interface available online that can be used via browser
Description	<p>This attribute describes how the service can be used/called.</p> <p>Mapping to SSHOC MP: always category “tool-or-service”, except for Instruction Page</p>
Mapping	<p>schema.org mapping NA</p> <p>SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool. P16i was used for: E7 Activity. P33 used specific technique: E29 Design or Procedure. P2 has type: E55 Type</p>
Example	source code/web application

Attribute	Condition of use: Local use
Repeatability	Optional, repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	Custom vocabulary: {free, free in specific context, freemium, subscription, paid licence }
Description	<p>This attribute is used to indicate under which terms the solution can be installed or operated locally.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free • Free in specific contexts (e.g. academic use, individual free licence) • Freemium (costs for specific additions such as support, unlimited calls) • Subscription (i.e. regular payments) • Paid licence (i.e. one time payment)
Mapping	<p>https://schema.org/isAccessibleForFree, https://schema.org/requiresSubscription, https://schema.org/conditionsOfAccess</p> <p>SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool. P104 is subject to right: E30 Right. P2 has type: E55 Type AND E55 Type. P2 has type: E55 Type {= “Local Use”}</p>
Example	free

Attribute	Condition of use: Operate service
Repeatability	Optional, repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	Custom vocabulary: {free, free in specific context, freemium, subscription, paid licence }
Description	<p>This attribute is used to indicate under which terms the solution can be installed or operated as a service and offered to third parties.</p> <p>See attribute “Condition of use: Local use” for definition of the used vocabulary.</p>
Mapping	<p>https://schema.org/isAccessibleForFree, https://schema.org/requiresSubscription, https://schema.org/conditionsOfAccess</p> <p>SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool. P104 is subject to right: E30 Right. P2 has type: E55 Type , AND E55 Type. P2 has type: E55 Type {= “Operate service”}</p>
Example	free

Attribute	Condition of use: Further development
Repeatability	Optional, repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	Custom vocabulary: {free, free in specific context, freemium, subscription, paid licence }
Description	<p>This attribute is used to indicate under which terms the solution can be integrated or changed.</p> <p>See attribute “Condition of use: Local use” for definition of the used vocabulary.</p>
Mapping	<p>https://schema.org/isAccessibleForFree, https://schema.org/requiresSubscription, https://schema.org/conditionsOfAccess</p> <p>SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool. P104 is subject to right: E30 Right. P2 has type: E55 Type , AND E55 Type. P2 has type: E55 Type {= “Future use”}</p>

Example	free
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Attribute	Terms of Use / License
Repeatability	Optional, repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	https://spdx.org/licenses/
Description	This attribute is the license document that applies to the solution, typically indicated by URL. .
Mapping	https://schema.org/license SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool. P104 is subject to right: E30 Right. P70i is documented in: E31 Document. PP50 accessible at: PE29 Access Point, AND E31 Document.P2 has type: E55 Type {= "Digital"}
Example	EUPLv1.2 https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/custom-page/attachment/2020-03/EUPL-1.2%20EN.txt

Attribute	Input format
Repeatability	Optional, repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/media-types.xhtml
Description	This attribute describes the media type (MIME type) of the input file(s).
Mapping	https://schema.org/encodingFormat (does not allow to specify that it is input format) SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool. P16i was used for: SHE4 Service. SHR4 had input: SHE1 Dataset. P2 has type: E55 Type , AND
Example	TextGrid/bin

Attribute	Input format comment
Repeatability	Optional, non-repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	
Description	This attribute provides further information on the input format.
Mapping	https://schema.org/Comment SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool. P16i was used for: SHE4 Service. SHR4 had input: SHE1 Dataset. P2 has type: E55 Type. P3 has note: E62 String
Example	API available for format independent input

Attribute	Output format
Repeatability	Optional, repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/media-types.xhtml
Description	This attribute describes the media type (MIME type) of the output file(s).
Mapping	https://schema.org/encodingFormat (does not allow to specify that it is output format) SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool. P16i was used for: SHE4 Service. SHR5 had output: SHE1 Dataset. P2 has type: E55 Type, AND
Example	csv

Attribute	Output format comment
Repeatability	Optional, non-repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	
Description	This attribute provides further information on the output format.

Mapping	https://schema.org/Comment SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool. P16i was used for: SHE4 Service. SHR5 had output: SHE1 Dataset. P2 has type: E55 Type. P3 has note: E63 String
Example	

Attribute	Status
Repeatability	Optional, repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	Custom vocabulary: { abandoned; finalized; finished; in development; maintained; no longer developed but still available; not maintained; unclear }
Description	This attribute describes the status of the solution in terms of its lifecycle stage. The custom vocabulary is partly based on https://wiki.de.dariah.eu/display/publicde/DARIAH-DE+Service+Life+Cycle
Mapping	https://schema.org/creativeWorkStatus SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool. P2 has type: E55 Type
Example	maintained

Attribute	Publication date
Repeatability	Optional, non-repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	ISO 8601 Date, see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_8601
Description	This attribute describes the time when the solution first appeared with the exact date or free text.
Mapping	https://schema.org/datePublished SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool.94i was created by: E65 Creation. P82 at some point within: E52 Time-Span. P79 beginning is qualified by: E62 String, AND E65 Creation. P2 has type: E55 Type {= "Publication"}
Example	2017-10-25

Attribute	Last modification date
Repeatability	Optional, non-repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	ISO 8601 Date, see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_8601
Description	This attribute describes the time when the solution was most recently modified with the exact date or free text.
Mapping	https://schema.org/dateModified SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool. P94i was created by: E65 Creation. P82 at some point within: E52 Time-Span. P80 end is qualified by: E62 String, AND E65 Creation. P2 has type: E55 Type {= "Modification"}
Example	2021-05-05

Attribute	Expected level of knowledge
Repeatability	Optional, non-repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	Custom vocabulary: { novice, advanced, expert }
Description	This attribute describes the level of knowledge the user of the solution is expected to have. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • novice = no specific background knowledge required; • advanced = some background knowledge required • expert = requires sound background knowledge and training in underlying concepts and technology
Mapping	schema.org mapping NA SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool. P2 has type: E55 Type {"novice"; "advanced"; "expert"} AND SHE10 Tool. P2 has type: E55 Type {= "Digital"}, AND SHE10 Tool. P2 has type: E55 Type {= "Conversion solution"}
Example	expert

Attribute	Application category
Repeatability	Optional, non-repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	Custom vocabulary: {data processing}
Description	This attribute describes the type of the solution and is used by the Marketplace. In schema.org this is a very broad category, such as "Game" or "Multimedia", but for Conversion Hubs, this is always "data processing" and subcategory specified as "conversion".
Mapping	https://schema.org/applicationCategory SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool.P2 has type: E55 Type AND SHE10 Tool.P2 has type: E55 Type {"Application category"}
Example	data processing

Attribute	Application sub-category
Repeatability	Optional, non-repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	Custom vocabulary: { conversion }
Description	This attribute describes the subtype of the solution and is used by the Marketplace. For Conversion Hub, this is always "conversion". (based on definition of https://schema.org/applicationSubCategory)
Mapping	https://schema.org/applicationSubCategory SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool.P2 has type: E55 Type AND SHE10 Tool.P2 has type: E55 Type {"Application subcategory"}
Example	conversion

Attribute	See Also
Repeatability	Optional, repeatable

Terms/vocabulary	
Description	URL + optional description (link text). This attribute describes resources that are related to the solution. For example, If there is a github/gitlab repository where you can get the source code.
Mapping	https://schema.org/isRelatedTo SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool. PP50 accessible at: PE29 Access Point
Example	

Attribute	Source
Repeatability	Optional, repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	
Description	URL + optional description (link text). This attribute describes the source(s) that were used to create the Conversion Hub entry.
Mapping	https://schema.org/isBasedOn SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool. P16i was used for: E65 Creation. P94 created: E73 Information Object. P2 has type: E55 Type {= "Conversion hub entry"}, AND E65 Creation. P2 has type: E55 Type {= "Conversion Activity"}
Example	Documentation of Kuha2 https://kuha2.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html

Attribute	Related Tool
Repeatability	Optional, repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	
Description	This attribute names a tool that is closely related to the conversion solution or the reason the conversion exists.

Mapping	https://schema.org/isRelatedTo SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool. P16i was used for: E65 Creation. P94 created: E73 Information Object. P2 has type: E55 Type {= "Digital"}, AND E65 Creation. P2 has type: E55 Type {= "Conversion Activity"}
Example	

Attribute	Is Recipe
Repeatability	Optional, non-repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	
Description	Indicates if the conversion solution is a recipe. A recipe includes i.e. the steps needed for conversion. The recipe is prose text (html).
Mapping	schema.org mapping NA SSHOCro: SHE10 Tool. P2 has type: E55 Type {"Recipe"} AND SHE10 Tool. P3 has note: E62 String
Example	

Attribute	Contact
Repeatability	Optional, repeatable
Terms/vocabulary	
Description	The main contact point of the described conversion solution.
Mapping	https://schema.org/ContactPoint SHE10 Tool. P1 is identified by: E41 Appellation
Example	